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The availability of critical minerals for Nigeria's renewable energy and economic development: an assessment of the role of nanotechnology

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ABSTRACT

Mineral assets form a major source of national wealth and can provide a country with an opportunity for economic development. Nigeria is rich in minerals identified as critical to the energy transition and can leverage nanotechnology to optimize these mineral resources for developing renewable energy, thereby improving her economy. This review aims to present the available minerals in Nigeria for clean energy production and how nanotechnology can be utilized to harness the potential of these mineral resources for sustainable development. We hope that this paper serves as a source of motivation for the government, researchers, and investors to promote nanotechnology as a tool for optimizing mineral resources, developing renewable energy, and improving the economy.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, Minerals, Renewable energy, National development, National wealth

1 INTRODUCTION

The world has awakened to the reality of the damage fossil fuels have done to nature due to the greenhouse gases they emit. As a result, a global campaign on a switch to cleaner energy technologies and achieving net zero carbon was launched. This is the target of Sustainable Development Goal 7, improving access to affordable, clean, and sustainable energy for all. However, the success of this energy transition hinges on a sustainable supply of some mineral resources and metals [1]. Interestingly, Africa holds an estimated 30% of the world's mineral reserves [2]. The International Energy Agency listed about 11 minerals critical in the transition to clean energy [3]. They are; copper, lithium, nickel, manganese, cobalt, graphite, chromium, molybdenum, zinc, rare earth, silicon, and others. 3 out of 6 recommendations by the IEA- investing in new supply, supporting the value chain with technology innovation, and stepping up recycling of used resources emphasized approaches to guarantee mineral security [3].

All these critical minerals are found in abundance in Nigeria positioning her as a strong support pillar for their supply. The country is believed to have about 76 minerals that are scattered across all the states of the federation [4]. The availability of minerals in specific locations of the country is indicated by the Geographical Survey of Nigerian mineral resources [5]. The lack of interest in this sector on the part of the government, however, is the only challenge setting us back. Nigeria currently ranks 23rd with 34.5 Mining Contribution Index (MCI) in Africa [6] due to the inactiveness of this sector despite its abundance of resources. The highest contribution of solid minerals to GDP recorded between 1981 and 2010 was 1.08% in 1981 & 1.12% in 1982 [7]. The sector contributed 0.26% to Nigeria's total GDP in 2019 and N686.64 billion (0.45%) to the total GDP of N152.32 trillion in 2020 [8]. Contribution to export was 0.14% compared to 0.51% in 2019 meaning most of the minerals produced are those used locally in Nigeria [8].

Nigeria can only play a vital role in the sustainable supply of these critical minerals with a domestic Mining Resource Corridor (MRC). The MRC has numerous economic benefits [9], but we must first resolve below factors that can be undermine it.

- Power source (electricity)
- exploitation technology (exploration/prospecting, appraisal, production, and utilization)
- infrastructure to access mining sites and transport materials
- social consequence of community displacement and loss of livelihood or property (land acquisition)
- environmental issues like ecological (pollution and encroachment)
- Insecurity - Insurgents, Boko Haram, bandits, and kidnappers

The existence of multiple regulations and the unavailability of accurate data [10] are also part of the concerns. There is a need to address these issues to maximize the potential of the MRC. The ongoing privatization of the mining companies [4] can also be integrated into the Mining Resource Corridor development.

As the Nigerian government, therefore, plan to increase the contribution of the solid minerals sector to the GDP to 5% [8] and possibly 10% by 2026 [11], Nanotechnology can help achieve that through the development of

nanoproducts for renewable energy use. These products will earn us more export earnings for the minerals than exporting them as raw crude ores or concentrates. In 2020, the ore and concentrates of zinc, lead, and manganese contributed 65% to the total export (21,590 tons) of about thirty minerals types from Nigeria, with China accounting for 80% and 85% of the total export volume and value, respectively [8]. Metallurgical processing (Intermediate phase) and manufacturing of nanoproducts (Downstream phase) will yield better revenue.

2 THE CRITICAL MINERALS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

In a study in 2021, the International Energy Agency highlighted about 11 minerals mostly used in selected clean energy technologies (Fig. 1) and tagged them as critical to the clean energy transition [3]. Nigeria is blessed with numerous natural resources, and these minerals are some of them.

Table 1 shows the location of the selected critical minerals in Nigeria while Fig. 2 is a map showing the distribution of the solid minerals in Nigeria. Ore reserves of over 10 million tons of lead ore and 100,000 tons of zinc ore are estimated, spread over eight states: Cross River, Ebonyi, Imo, Benue, Nassarawa, Plateau, Taraba, and Zamfara [6]. Lithium deposits exist in Kogi, Nasarawa, Ekiti, Kwara, Cross River, Oyo, Plateau, and a few other states, while graphite is available in Kaduna and Adamawa states in Nigeria [13]. Nigeria’s copper ore deposit is estimated to be over 10,000,000 tons [14] and is found in Nasarawa [15]. A large nickel deposit is at Dangoma, Kaduna State [16]. Manganese [17, 18], Rare-earth elements [19 – 21] and Silica [22] are all found in Nigeria.

Fig. 1. IEA Selected critical minerals for clean energy transitions [3]

Fig. 2. Map of Nigeria showing distribution of solid minerals [12]

Some other valuable minerals exist in Nigeria. The Segilola Gold deposit Mineral Resource comprises an Indicated resource of 4.06 Mt @ 4.66 g/t Au for 608,000 ounces of gold and an Inferred resource of 0.443 Mt @ 4.8 g/t Au for 68,000 ounces of gold [23]. Iron Ore (estimated 2.5 billion tons), Chromite, Titanium, Uranium, Silver, Cassiterite (Tin ore), and Diamond are all found in Nigeria.

Table 1. Selected minerals in Nigeria for clean energy transitions

S/N	MINERAL	LOCATION	Reference/Remarks
1	Copper	Zamfara, Bauchi, Kano, Yobe, Nasarawa, Plateau, Jigawa, Katsina	[15, 16, 24, 25]
2	Lithium	Kogi, Nasarawa, Ekiti, Kwara, Cross River, Oyo, Plateau	[13] Lithium was successfully extracted from Ekiti clays. Nigeria clays is >120 million tonnes [26]
3	Nickel	Kaduna, Osun, Katsina	[25, 27]
4	Manganese	Niger, Edo, Adamawa, Kebbi, Borno, Cross River, Kaduna, Zamfara, Katsina	[16, 17, 18, 24]
5	Cobalt	Adamawa, Kaduna, Katsina	Cobalt is licensed in Adamawa and Kaduna [11]; Cobalt occurrence in Nigeria [24]; [25]
6	Graphite	Kaduna, Adamawa, Niger, Bauchi; Cross River, Jigawa	[13, 19, 25, 28, 29, 30]
7	Chromium	Zamfara, Katsina, Kaduna, Kogi	[16]
8	Molybdenum	Plateau, Ondo	[12, 16]
9	Zinc	Cross River, Ebonyi, Benue, Nassarawa, Plateau, Taraba, Zamfara	[12, 16]
10	Rare earths	Ebonyi, Plateau	[20, 21]

11	Silica Sand (Silicon)	Abia, AkwaIbom, Anambra, Bayelsa, Benue, Bornu, Cross River, Delta, Enugu, Imo, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Lagos, Nasarawa, Ondo, Niger, Ogun, Rivers, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara	[22]
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3 THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNECHNOLOGY

Nanotechnology has made possible the development of Nanostructured materials such as nano-enabled tubes, sensors, coolants, coatings, cables, fasteners, batteries, and super capacitors. These nanoproductions that can be made from mineral resources have significant applications in almost all sustainable energy technologies, such as solar energy, wind energy, tidal, geothermal, hydrogen, and biofuels. Nanoproductions can shape the nature of modern life, the social environment, and the country's economy. The process involved in creating these products will improve the industrial sector, develop the host communities, creates wealth for people and government, improves the standard of living and quality of life, and consequently bring about economic growth and sustainable development. Nanotechnology can increase the conversion efficiency of solar collectors, enhance energy storage devices and improve thermal energy storage in residential areas and industrial regions [31]. Some nanoproductions from these minerals and areas of application are also further presented to confirm the versatility of Nanotechnology.

3.1 Solar energy application

3.1.1 Nanoparticles and Nanofluids for solar energy or thermal conversion and storage

One of the significant applications of Nanoparticles (NPs) is in enhancing solar energy technologies, especially energy or thermal conversion and storage. Researchers have successfully improved the performance of solar energy systems with NPs such as Zinc oxide nanowires and cuprous oxide NPs [32], Silica NPs [33], Graphite NPs [34], Zn micron-sized particles [35], Copper NPs [36 – 38], Cobalt NPs [39], Iron oxide NPs [40], Flake graphite NPs [41], Black chromium, Cr/Cr₂O₃ [42], Neodymium and Erbium NPs [43], Manganese NPs [44], Molybdenum NPs [45], Manganese oxide, MnO₂ [46], SiO₂ [47], Zinc oxide, ZnO [48, 49], and Spinel Cu-Mn-Cr oxide [50]. Perovskite solar cells were also made more efficient with the Electrodeposition of Lithium-based LiYF₄=Yb³⁺, Er³⁺ upconversion (UC) thin films [51].

Nanofluids (NF) from varieties of nanoparticles can also enhance solar energy or thermal conversion and storage. Some of the nanofluids with great solar energy application potential confirmed by researchers are: carbon nanotubes, graphite, and silver [52], MgO-Water Nanofluids [53], cobalt oxide (Co₃O₄) based nanofluid [54], magnesium oxide (MgO) and nickel (Ni) nanofluid [55], photothermal conversion of common Al₂O₃- γ , Si, Cu, Zn, Fe and Ag - based nanofluids [56], Graphite/nanodiamond suspension [57], metallic copper NF [58], Zinc oxide/Ethylene glycol and Deionized water [59], Zinc oxide [60], water/zinc oxide nanofluid [61] and Ag/Cr₂O₃ NPs [62].

3.1.2 Nanofluids as coolant for Li ion batteries: Nanofluids were applied to solve heat loss challenges limiting the efficiency of Li-ion batteries. Manganese oxide-water-based nanofluids [63], TiO₂, ZnO, and diamond nanofluids [64], Al₂O₃-based nanofluids [65] were all reported as potential coolants for Li-ion batteries.

3.2 Geothermal Energy Applications

In geothermal systems, nanofluids can enhance heat transfer and reduce the size of heat exchangers [66]. Nanofluids can also encapsulate or absorb substantially higher orders of energy better than normal thermal fluids, thereby providing a solution to the challenge of deep borings, which often cause tremors or earthquakes and limit the utilization of geothermal energy [67].

3.3 Water splitting and oxygen reduction for hydrogen production

Cobalt NPs [68], Nickel nanoparticles [69], silver, iron, titanium oxide, and nickel-based inorganic particles [70], Nickel nanopowder [71], Cobalt phosphide, Co₂P [72], FeCo alloy nanoparticles [73] performed great as potential nanoparticles for hydrogen production. Hydrogen was also generated from seawater using Manganese doped nickel oxide/nickel as electrocatalysts [74].

3.4 Biofuel production

Nanomaterials have also enhanced the production of biofuel. Nanosized cerium oxide particles reduced the emission levels of hydrocarbons and NO_x components of biodiesel fuel when added to it [75]. Biodiesel was also produced from Mahua oil using Manganese-doped zinc oxide as a nanocatalyst [76].

3.5 Wind energy

Patel and Mahajan [77] reported an extensive area of applications of Nanomaterials in wind energy in their work. Carbon Nanotube (CNT), Carbon nanofibers (CNFs), Multi-walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNT), and Graphene platelets have successfully been used to improve the design, features, and efficiency of Turbine blades. Graphene and Tungsten sulfide nanoparticles have been used as lubricants in Gearbox bearings. Nanofluid from water and alumina nanoparticles have been tested as alternative cooling system for wind turbine. Cables made from CNT are also good materials for electrical cables for transmission of power in wind farms.

New areas are currently being explored. Nano-colloidal lubricant additives combined with borided surfaces improved the wear resistance, making it suitable for application in wind turbine gearbox [78].

4. PRACTICAL STEPS TO ACHIEVE RENEWABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT AND ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY

1. Diversify the economy to focus on solid mineral development.

The solid minerals sector is one of the sectors strongly recommended to diversify our current oil-based economy [79]. Solid minerals are raw materials for preparing inorganic nanoparticles. It is key to renewable energy and sustainable development. Investing in renewable energy is currently the best option for electricity generation [80]

and a reduction in GHG emissions [81]. The location of the mineral resources influences the siting of industries to exploit these minerals and downstream industries utilizing the by-products of these industries, consequently resulting in city development, job creation, and tourist attractions [5]. Infrastructure development is significant to poverty reduction [82].

2. Create research facilities for nanotechnology and other smart technologies.

The government should establish centers for Nanotechnology, sponsor scientific research in this area, and encourage partnerships between academics and the industry. The increasing global energy consumption will require new and smart technologies to produce energy in the most efficient manner [83]. The centers of excellence will facilitate the commercial production of inorganic nanoparticles from solid minerals and promote advancement in the field.

3. Reduce the cost of doing business locally and for foreign investors.

Private investors should also be encouraged by providing an enabling environment and favorable cost of doing business. The solid minerals sector contributed N116.80 billion (3.42%) to the total revenue of N3.42 trillion generated by the Federal Government in 2020, and the bulk of it was from taxes [8]. The cost of doing business is a challenge [84] and further disincentives investors. There is a need to improve the investment environment to attract the scarce exploration and mining capital needed [85] to develop the mineral resources sector.

4. Encourage recycling, particularly metal recycling.

Metal recycling should also be prioritized [86] to sustain the nation's solid mineral deposits, especially the metallic ores. This approach will further strengthen the sustainability of the critical minerals supply chain for clean energy transitions.

5. Back up compliance with the energy transition program with effective policies and ensure implementation.

Policy review and effective implementation are paramount for a successful energy transition program [87, 88]. Implementation is key so as not to make it another policy on paper.

5 RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations will assist Nigeria, Africa, and other mineral-rich developing countries to maximize nanotechnology as a tool for optimising mineral resources for renewable energy development and economic sustainability.

- Develop a mining resource corridor and embrace smart technologies to maximize the potential of solid minerals.
- The government should create nanotechnology research centres and facilitate collaboration between industry and academics through research sponsorship.

- Create an enabling environment for investors and promote public-private partnerships.
- Encourage metal recycling.
- Formulate policies on the energy transition or review existing ones and ensure effective implementation.

6 CONCLUSION

Sustainable Development Goal 7 is focused on access to clean and affordable energy, which is key to economic and human development. One way to fast-track the achievement of this goal is to leverage current and new technologies. In this study, a review of the critical minerals in Nigeria and how nanotechnology can be leveraged to transform them for renewable energy development and economic stability was done. This work hereby gives rise to the following conclusion:

1. Nigeria is rich in minerals critical to clean energy transition and other mineral resources.
2. Nanotechnology is one of such technologies that can be leveraged to optimize Nigeria's mineral resources for renewable energy and economic development. Nanotechnology can effectively produce nanoproducts like nanoparticles and nanofluids for local use and export. Processing the crude minerals will yield better economic gain than selling them unrefined.
3. Energy transitions and Nanotechnology can drive the development of a domestic Mining Resource Corridor. However, strong government commitment (infrastructure development, compensation, regulations, security, etc.) must back-up execution or implementation to be successful. An investment in Nanotechnology for the development of the critical minerals will invariably result into infrastructural development.
4. Developing the critical mineral resources value chain will also increase export and revenue, provide employment opportunities, develop local communities, better citizens' standard of living, and improve economic sustainability.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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